

Metal Complexes of Thiopolycarboxylic Acids (II) : Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) Complexes with Methylenebisthiopropionic Acid and Methylenebisthioacetic Acid

S. K. TIWARI, A. KUMAR, (MRS.) S. JAIN and N. P. PARASHAR

Chemical Laboratories, Z. H. College of Engineering and Technology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh

Manuscript received 25 February 1976; revised 21 June 1976; accepted 5 July 1976

Complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) with methylenebisthiopropionic acid and methylenebisthioacetic acid were prepared and their possible structures discussed on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility and infrared spectral studies. The results are in agreement with the tetrahedral arrangement of the coordination sphere of the metal ions studied.

THE metal complexes of thiopolycarboxylic acids, as thio analogs of complexones, have been the subject of many recent studies¹⁻⁵. Thiopolycarboxylic acids contain two or more thio and carboxylic groups as potential donors and therefore capable of combining in various polydentate mode.

In continuation of our work on metal complexes of thiopolycarboxylic acids⁵, the present paper deals with the preparation and characterisation of methylenebisthiopropionic acid (MBTPA-H₂), CH₂(S.CH₂-CH₂.COOH)₂ and methylenebisthioacetic acid (MBTAA-H₂), CH₂(S.CH₂.COOH)₂ complexes with Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II). A difference in interaction of these cations is not unexpected because of their affinity towards sulphur which falls in order Zn(II) < Cd(II) ≪ Hg(II).

Experimental

Chemicals. MBTPA-H₂ of 98.8% purity and MBTAA-H₂ of 99.5% purity (Evans Chematics, New York) were used without further purification. All other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of the metal complexes. MBTPA-H₂ and MBTAA-H₂ form solid complexes with Zn, Cd and Hg ions. These compounds were prepared by the same general method described below, using metal acetates, with reference to the Zn(II)-MBTPA-H₂ complex.

30 ml aqueous solution of 0.2M zinc acetate was added to an equimolar solution of MBTPA-H₂ (90 ml) in alcohol. The reaction mixture was then heated and subsequently cooled and then kept in a refrigerator for two days for crystallisation. The white coloured complex was then filtered, washed with alcohol and ether and then dried in vacuum over CaCl₂.

Complexes of Cd(II) and Hg(II), in white and whitish yellow colour respectively, were prepared by similar method.

Physical measurements. The instruments and methods have been given previously⁵.

Results and Discussion

Results are given in Table 1. The molar conductance of soluble complexes in DMSO indicates the non-electrolytic nature of these complexes. They are all diamagnetic, as expected, and their electronic spectra was practically identical with that of their corresponding ligands.

The infrared spectra of the ligands and the complexes were recorded in region 4000-400 cm⁻¹. The important bands and their tentative assignments, (Table 2) were obtained with reference to the spectra of other carboxylate complexes and as well as those of thio and amino acid complexes¹⁻¹⁰. The complexes of thiopolycarboxylic acids with bivalent mercury differ in their properties considerably from those with transition metals, zinc and cadmium, respectively. This is obviously due to great affinity of mercury towards sulphidic sulphur. The comparison of infrared spectra of MBTPA-H₂ and MBTAA-H₂ with those of respective complexes, (Table 2) suggests that the coordination sphere, in Cd(MBTPA), Hg(MBTPA) and Hg(MBTAA) complexes is formed by two sulphur atoms and two oxygen atoms. The position of the bands of antisymmetric stretching vibrations of the carboxylic group as well as the difference of the antisymmetric and symmetric vibrations, Δ(COO), always higher than 220 cm⁻¹ indicate the covalent character of the carboxyl-metal bond¹¹⁻¹². The (C-S) stretching vibrations of the ligands shifted to lower frequencies in these complexes, similar to analogous systems of thiopolycarboxylic metal chelates^{1,2,4,5}, indicating the coordination through sulphur. On the other hand, in Cd(MBTPA), Zn(MBTPA) and Zn(MBTAA) complexes, infrared spectra indicates unambiguously that sulphur is not coordinated to the metal ions. The

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND DECOMPOSITION TEMPERATURES OF MBTPA-H₂ AND MBTAA-H₂ COMPLEXES

Compound	%Metal		%Carbon		%Hydrogen		%Sulphur		Molar conductance in DMSO ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	Decomposition Temp. °C
	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found		
Zn(C ₇ H ₁₀ S ₂ O ₄).H ₂ O	21.38	21.46	27.51	27.42	3.95	3.86	20.97	20.87	Insoluble	110
Cd(C ₇ H ₁₀ S ₂ O ₄)	35.71	35.60	26.61	26.56	3.28	3.34	20.37	20.10	Insoluble	80
Hg(C ₇ H ₁₀ S ₂ O ₄).4H ₂ O	40.53	40.48	16.98	17.03	3.66	3.60	12.95	12.86	4.2	130
Zn(C ₈ H ₈ S ₂ O ₄).H ₂ O	23.55	23.48	21.64	21.83	2.90	2.93	23.10	23.01	Insoluble	160
Cd(C ₈ H ₈ S ₂ O ₄)	40.93	40.81	21.87	21.80	2.20	2.12	23.35	23.15	3.1	280
Hg(C ₈ H ₈ S ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O	46.55	46.72	13.93	13.83	2.34	2.25	14.88	14.73	4.5	150

TABLE 2—TENTATIVE ASSIGNMENTS OF IMPORTANT INFRARED BANDS OF MBTPA, MBTAA AND THEIR Zn(II), Cd(II) AND Hg(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Tentative assignments						
	$\nu(\text{C-S})$	$-(\text{OH})$ deformation	$\nu(\text{COO})_{\text{sym}}$	$\nu(\text{COO})_{\text{asym}}$	$\delta(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	$\Delta\nu(\text{COO})$
(C ₇ H ₁₂ S ₂ O ₄)	740(s)	815(m)	1430(s)	1700(s)	—	—	270
Zn(C ₇ H ₁₀ S ₂ O ₄).H ₂ O	745(m)	—	1400(s)	1580(s)	1670(m)	3150(w)	180
Cd(C ₇ H ₁₀ S ₂ O ₄)	740(m)	—	1420(s)	1580(s)	—	—	160
Hg(C ₇ H ₁₀ S ₂ O ₄).4H ₂ O	710(m)	—	1400(m)	1650(s)	1665(m)	3200(sbr.)	250
(C ₈ H ₈ S ₂ O ₄)	730(s)	810(m)	1410(s)	1710(s)	—	—	300
Zn(C ₈ H ₈ S ₂ O ₄).H ₂ O	730(m)	—	1390(m)	1580(s)	1665(m)	3150(w.br)	190
Cd(C ₈ H ₈ S ₂ O ₄)	710(m)	—	1370(m)	1640(s)	—	—	270
Hg(C ₈ H ₈ S ₂ O ₄).2H ₂ O	705(m)	—	1400(m)	1660(s)	1665(m)	3150(mbr)	260

s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, br = broad.

antisymmetric (COO) stretching vibrations of these complexes shifted to lower frequency in the region 1560–1590 cm⁻¹ and $\Delta(\text{COO})$ was always less than 220 cm⁻¹. These values correspond to those of glycinate and other amino acid complexes^{7,13}. The bridging carboxylic groups of metal carboxylate complexes also show an absorption in this region. Therefore, in Cd(MBTPA), Zn(MBTPA) and Zn(MBTAA) complexes, metal ions are coordinated by oxygen atoms only. The coordination of carboxylic oxygen, in all these complexes, studied was further supported by the disappearance of -OH deformation vibrations. Other characteristic band groups in the infrared spectra lead to the conclusion that hydrated water (if present) does not take part in the coordination and that the carboxyl-metal bond has essentially an ionic character¹².

For the consideration of steric arrangement of the complexes, it is possible to assume 4-coordinated tetrahedral (sp³ bond type) structure, which is most usual for bivalent zinc, cadmium and mercury⁴. Therefore, in Cd(MBTPA), Zn(MBTPA) and Zn(MBTAA) complexes, metal ions are coordinated tetrahedrally by oxygen atoms as donors and coordination sphere is formed alternately by bonding and non-bonding oxygen atoms of the carboxyl-group. The insolubility indicates that non-bonding oxygen atoms are supplied by neighbouring ligand molecules in the formation of a polymeric network.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to M/s Evans Chemetics Inc., New York for the gift samples of MBTPA-H₂

and MBTAA-H₂. One of the authors (A.K.) is thankful to C.S.I.R. (New Delhi) for the award of a senior research fellowship. The authors are also grateful to Dr. K. C. Tewari, Reader in the Chemistry Department, for valuable suggestions and Prof. W. Rahman and Prof. M. Qureshi for providing research facilities.

References

1. J. PODLAHA and J. PODLAHOVA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1970, 4, 521, 549.
2. J. PODLAHA and J. PODLAHOVA, *Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1971, 5, 413, 920.
3. J. PODLAHOVA, J. LOUB and C. NOVAK, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1972, B28, 1623.
4. O. PROCHAZKOVA, J. PODLAHOVA and J. PODLAHA, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1973, 38, 1120, 1128.
5. A. KUMAR, S. JAIN and S. K. TIWARI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 37, 2439.
6. S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Quart. Rev.*, 1965, 19, 386.
7. C. A. MCAULIFFE and W. D. PERRY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, A634.
8. K. NAKAMOTO, 'Infrared spectra of Inorganic and Coordination compounds', John Wiley & Sons, New York (N.Y.), 1963.
9. C. G. BARRALLOUGH, R. L. MARTIN and I. M. STEWART, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1969, 22, 891.
10. S. E. WIBERLEY, S. C. BUNCE and W. H. BANNER, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1960, 32, 217.
11. E. K. NAKAMOTO and P. J. MCCARTHY, 'Spectroscopy and Structure of Metal Chelate compounds', Wiley, New York, 1968.
12. D. T. SAWYER, *Ann. N.Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1960, 88, 307.
13. C. A. MCAULIFFE, J. V. QUAGLIANO and L. M. VALLARINO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1996.